

Fake News Detection with Deep Learning, Fine-Tuned Transformers, and LLM-Generated Rationales

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Abstract—The proliferation of fake news across the internet and social media has created significant challenges in terms of societal, political, financial, and health-related implications. This study addresses the urgent need for accurate and efficient fake news detection by utilizing machine learning (ML), deep learning (DL), and large language models (LLMs). Building on earlier work that mainly used traditional ML and data mining methods, this research explores advanced DL techniques, including BERT-based transformers and large language models, to enhance detection accuracy. Using a public Kaggle dataset comprising 7,796 news articles (balanced between real and fake), we evaluate multiple models, including Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, CNN, LSTM, and hybrid CNN-LSTM architectures, as well as transformer models such as BERT, RoBERTa, DistilBERT, ALBERT, ELECTRA, and FinBERT. The results demonstrate that RoBERTa with RoBERTaTokenizer achieves the highest performance with an accuracy of 99.84%, outperforming traditional ML and DL models. Furthermore, zero-shot evaluations using ChatGPT, Gemini, and DeepSeek disclose that LLMs can reliably classify news articles without fine-tuning, with Gemini and DeepSeek showing stronger generalization than ChatGPT in certain cases. This study highlights the effectiveness of transformer-based models and LLMs in advancing the robustness and reliability of fake news detection tasks.

Index Terms—Fake News Detection, Deep Learning, Transformer Models, Large Language Models

I. INTRODUCTION

The internet and the growth of social media have dramatically changed how people share and receive information. Unlike traditional media, where content usually goes through editing and verification before publication, online platforms make it possible for information to spread instantly to large audiences with very little review or oversight [1]. This change has facilitated rapid access to news and facilitated the uncontrolled spread of misinformation and fake news. Fake news, defined as false or misleading information presented as legitimate news, poses serious risks across multiple sectors. Socially, it can lead to public confusion, harassment, and erosion of trust [2], [3]. Politically, it has the potential to manipulate voter behavior, as demonstrated by the fact that the issue of fake news online gained significant attention during the 2016 US presidential election. Public safety has been put at risk by health-related misinformation during international

crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic, and the financial industry has suffered stock price manipulation and reputational damage as a result of the spread of fake news [4].

Detecting fake news is an inherently challenging task. The subtle differences between real and fake content, the different intentions behind social media communications, and the dynamic nature of online information ecosystems all contribute to the complexity [5]. Consequently, the development of robust, automated detection systems has become a pressing need. While prior studies have primarily focused on traditional machine learning (ML) and data mining techniques for fake news detection, there remains a significant gap in the exploration of deep learning (DL) methods and large language models (LLMs). Emerging approaches based on transformers, especially BERT, RoBERTa, and their derivatives, offer promising capabilities by capturing subtle textual representations that are crucial for distinguishing fake news from real news [6], [7].

This research aims to bridge this gap by systematically evaluating a broad set of machine learning, deep learning, and LLM techniques on a benchmark dataset. Our contributions include a comparative analysis of ensemble methods, CNNs, LSTMs, and transformer-based architectures, along with an evaluation of LLMs like ChatGPT¹, Gemini², and DeepSeek³ under zero-shot settings. Through this work, we aim to advance the understanding and effectiveness of automated fake news detection systems.

A. Contributions of the Paper

This paper makes the following key contributions:

- 1) **Comprehensive Evaluation of Methods:** We systematically evaluate traditional machine learning techniques (Random Forest, Gradient Boosting), deep learning models (CNN, LSTM, CNN-LSTM), and advanced transformer-based architectures (BERT, RoBERTa, DistilBERT, ALBERT, ELECTRA, and FinBERT [8]) for the task of fake news detection.

¹<https://openai.com/index/chatgpt/>

²<https://gemini.google.com/>

³<https://www.deepseek.com/>

- 2) Exploration of large language models (LLMs): We extend the evaluation to large language models (ChatGPT, Gemini, and DeepSeek) using zero-shot settings to assess their capability in classifying fake news without additional fine-tuning.
- 3) Benchmark Dataset Analysis: Using a publicly available Kaggle dataset comprising 7,796 labeled news articles (real and fake), we perform an 80-20 train-test split and standardize our experimental setup across all models for fair comparison.

In the remainder of this paper, related work is presented in Section II, the methodology is described in Section III, Section IV discusses the results and analysis, and Section V presents the conclusion and future work.

II. RELATED WORKS

The research presented in this paper represents several key topics, including fall detection and language models. This section reviews some of the state-of-the-art works closely related to our study.

A. Detecting Fake News using Machine Learning

Deepfake news, which relies on advanced generation techniques to produce highly realistic but false content, is becoming increasingly difficult to detect. To address this challenge, researchers have turned to machine learning, which can learn distinguishing patterns from large collections of real and fake articles. In practice, these models capture signals such as writing style, word choice, and sentiment or emotional tone, enabling faster and often more consistent detection than manual review. As a result, a range of classical machine learning methods has been widely adopted for fake news detection, including Random Forest [9], [10], Gradient Boosting [11], Support Vector Machines [12], Naive Bayes [13], and k-Nearest Neighbors [14].

B. Detecting Fake News using Deep Learning

The rapid spread of fake news has become a serious concern, especially as deepfake content grows more convincing and harder to spot. Many traditional detection techniques struggle with these sophisticated forgeries because they often rely on surface-level cues that can be easily mimicked. In contrast, deep learning offers a more flexible and powerful alternative by learning complex patterns directly from large collections of real and fake news. For example, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [15], [16], Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) [17], and transformer-based models can capture subtle signals in writing style, semantics, and context that may indicate manipulation. Beyond the text itself, Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) [18] can incorporate relationships among articles, users, and sources, which often provide additional evidence for improving detection accuracy. Researchers also use Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) to create challenging synthetic examples for training and to better understand how realistic fake content is generated. Overall, by modeling deeper structure, stylistic cues, and even emotional

signals in language, deep learning systems trained on large-scale datasets can achieve strong performance and help limit the impact of online misinformation [19].

C. Detecting Fake News using Transformers and Large Language Models

Transformer-based models have significantly advanced how machines read and interpret text. Architectures such as BERT [20] and RoBERTa utilize self-attention to capture long-range context and subtle linguistic cues, allowing them to uncover deeper meaning in news articles beyond surface-level keywords. More recently, LLMs [21] such as GPT and T5, have further raised the bar by training on massive text corpora, which helps them develop a richer understanding of language, style, and discourse. Because of this, these models can often distinguish real from fake news by picking up on small inconsistencies in context, tone, and narrative flow. Overall, combining transformer encoders and modern LLMs offers a strong foundation for detecting deepfake-style misinformation and limiting its spread online [22]–[26].

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Dataset and Preprocessing

The dataset used in this study was obtained from Kaggle⁴ and consists of 7,796 samples with four columns: an identifier, the title of the news article, the main text content, and a label indicating whether the news is REAL or FAKE. The dataset has a shape of 7796×4 and occupies approximately 29.2 MB of storage. The labels are nearly balanced between real and fake news, ensuring that the models do not become biased toward a particular class during training. Each news article provides both the headline and the full text, offering rich linguistic information for detection models to utilize. The dataset covers diverse topics, including political events, international affairs, and general news, reflecting the types of content commonly seen on social media and news websites.

The process begins by preprocessing the news dataset, where the title and body text are concatenated to form a single input sequence. The labels are encoded into binary classes, with “FAKE” mapped to 0 and “REAL” mapped to 1. An 80%-20% train-test split is applied to ensure a fair evaluation. Minimal data cleaning was required, allowing the direct application of tokenization techniques such as TF-IDF vectorization and transformer-based tokenizers like BERT and RoBERTa.

B. Evaluation Metrics.

For evaluation metrics, we use accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. Additionally, the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve and Area Under the Curve (AUC) are plotted, providing a visual and quantitative assessment of the classifier’s discriminative ability.

⁴<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/clmentbisaillon/fake-and-real-news-dataset>

Fig. 1. Confusion Matrices of Ensemble Methods.

C. Ensemble Methods-Based Fake News Detection

Ensemble methods are a class of machine learning techniques that combine the predictions of multiple base models to produce a more robust and accurate final prediction. In the context of fake news detection, ensemble methods offer significant advantages by reducing model variance, mitigating overfitting, and enhancing generalization performance. In this study, we employed two widely used ensemble algorithms:

- 1) **Random Forest:** Random Forest is an ensemble learning method that builds a collection of decision trees during training and outputs the mode of the classes for classification tasks [9]. It is known for its robustness against overfitting and its ability to effectively handle high-dimensional datasets. In this study, we combine the Random Forest classifier with BERT-based embeddings to detect fake news with high accuracy. To generate semantic-rich features, we utilize the BERT-base-uncased model to extract dense vector embeddings for each news article. Mean pooling is applied over the last hidden states to obtain a fixed-length representation for each text sample. These BERT embeddings capture both syntactic and semantic nuances that are essential for differentiating between fake and real news. A Random Forest Classifier with 100 estimators (trees) and a fixed random state is then trained on the BERT-derived embeddings.
- 2) **Gradient Boosting:** In the first model, we apply a Gradient Boosting Classifier using TF-IDF vectorized features for fake news detection. The dataset was prepared by merging the title and text fields into a single input sequence. The text data was transformed using

Fig. 2. Confusion Matrices of Deep Learning Methods.

TF-IDF vectorization, which converts the text into a numerical representation by considering term frequency and inverse document frequency, with a maximum of 5000 features. These sparse representations were used as input to a gradient boosting classifier configured with 100 estimators, a learning rate of 0.1, and a maximum tree depth of 3.

D. Deep Learning Methods-Based Fake News Detection

Deep learning models show remarkable performance in natural language processing tasks, including fake news detection. In this study, we implement CNNs and LSTMs to classify news articles as real or fake, using both TF-IDF-vectorized text and BERT-generated embeddings.

- 1) **Convolution Neural Network (CNN):** A CNN is used for fake news detection with two types of inputs: TF-IDF features and BERT embeddings. For TF-IDF, news articles were vectorized to capture word importance across the corpus. For BERT-based input, texts were tokenized and embedded using BERT's pretrained model. After an 80-20 train-validation split, the BERT embeddings (size 768) were passed through a 1D convolutional layer with 256 channels and a kernel size of 3, followed by ReLU activation and adaptive max pooling. A final layer takes these learned features and decides whether the article

Fig. 3. Confusion Matrices of Transformer Methods.

is REAL or FAKE. We trained all models for three epochs, using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 2×10^{-5} , a batch size of 16, and Cross-Entropy Loss to measure performance.

- 2) Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM): We combine BERT’s contextual embeddings with a bidirectional LSTM for fake news detection. To turn the text into something the model can understand, we use the BERT tokenizer and then process it with the BERT model itself. We pass the results into a BiLSTM layer to better capture context in both directions. From there, we take the final output, apply dropout to help prevent overfitting, and run it through a linear classification layer. Finally, we train the model for two epochs with Adam, using a learning rate of 2×10^{-5} and cross-entropy loss.

A second model follows the same structure but uses ELECTRA instead of BERT. Texts were tokenized with ElectraTokenizer (ELECTRA-base-discriminator), embedded, passed through a BiLSTM, and classified similarly, using the same training settings.

- 3) CNN + LSTM: To build our fake news detector, we used a hybrid approach that processes text with BERT and then analyzes the resulting embeddings using both a CNN and an LSTM network. The model freezes

BERT parameters to extract embeddings, applies a 1D convolution to capture local features, and passes the output to a bidirectional LSTM with 64 hidden units per direction. A dropout layer and a fully connected layer finalize the classification. Trained for two epochs using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 2×10^{-5} .

E. Transformer Models-Based Fake News Detection

Transformer models have transformed natural language processing by using self-attention mechanisms to efficiently capture long-range dependencies and complex relationships in text, unlike traditional recurrent networks. In this work, we explore several transformer-based models for fake news detection, including BERT, RoBERTa, DistilBERT, ALBERT, ELECTRA, and FinBERT. We begin by fine-tuning BERT-base-uncased (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers), a model capable of deeply understanding word context by attending to both left and right surroundings. The news dataset, combining titles and texts, was tokenized using the BERT tokenizer, split into an 80-20 train-validation ratio, and fine-tuned with the Adam optimizer 2×10^{-5} using cross-entropy loss. Similarly, RoBERTa-base (Robustly Optimized BERT Pretraining Approach) was fine-tuned for binary classification, with news articles tokenized by the RoBERTa tokenizer and processed through RobertaForSequenceClassification, setting problem-type=‘single-label-classification’ to ensure correct application of Cross-Entropy loss. DistilBERT-base-uncased, a lightweight and faster version of BERT, was also fine-tuned for the same task, where tokenized news articles were processed using DistilBertForSequenceClassification and optimized over two epochs with AdamW optimizer.

For further efficiency, ALBERT-base-v2 (A Lite BERT) was employed, utilizing parameter sharing and factorized embeddings to reduce model size while retaining performance. The dataset was preprocessed, tokenized with the ALBERT tokenizer, and fine-tuned using AlbertForSequenceClassification. ELECTRA (Efficiently Learning an Encoder that Classifies Token Replacements Accurately) was also explored, where a discriminator-based pretraining objective allows for efficient learning; although mistakenly labeled as ALBERT in one section, ELECTRA follows a similar fine-tuning setup for news classification. Finally, we utilized FinBERT, a BERT model fine-tuned on financial text, adapting it for fake news detection. News articles were tokenized using the FinBERT tokenizer, and the classification head was adjusted for two output classes by setting ignore-mismatched-sizes during model loading.

Across all models, training was conducted for two epochs using the AdamW optimizer with a learning rate of 2×10^{-5} .

F. Large Language-Based Models-Based Fake News Detection

In addition to traditional machine learning and deep learning models, this study experiments with LLMs for fake news detection. We use ChatGPT, Gemini, and DeepSeek in a zero-shot setting, where each model classifies news articles as real or fake without task-specific fine-tuning. Given their massive pretraining on diverse corpora, these models can generalize

Fig. 4. ROC Curve of Ensemble models.

Fig. 5. ROC Curve of Deep Learning Models.

well to new tasks based solely on natural language prompts. For the evaluation, sample news headlines were provided to each LLM, and their outputs were compared against the actual labels.

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

1) *Ensemble Methods*: As in Table I using TF-IDF vectorization, Random Forest achieved an accuracy of 92.19%, an F1-score of 92.28%, a precision of 91.93%, a recall of 92.64%, and an AUC of 0.9751. Gradient boosting, by contrast, obtained an accuracy of 89.11%, an F1-score of 89.05%, a precision of 90.34%, a recall of 87.79%, and an AUC of 0.9654. These results were consistent when BERT tokenization was applied, with Random Forest reaching an accuracy of 89.58%, an F1-score of 89.46%, a precision of 91.35%, a recall of 87.64%, and an AUC of 0.9632, while

Gradient Boosting achieved an accuracy of 90.92%, an F1-score of 91.05%, a precision of 90.56%, a recall of 91.55%, and an AUC of 0.9715. Examination of the confusion matrices, as in Figure 1 indicated that Random Forest consistently produced fewer false negatives and false positives compared to Gradient Boosting, contributing to its higher overall F1-scores and balanced performance. These findings validate the effectiveness of ensemble methods, particularly Random Forest, in providing reliable fake news detection based on both traditional vectorization and transformer-based tokenization approaches.

2) *Deep Learning Methods*: Deep learning models were extensively evaluated for fake news detection using multiple performance metrics. As in Table I using TF-IDF vectorization, CNN achieved an accuracy of 89.11%, an F1-score of 89.05%, a precision of 90.34%, a recall of 87.79%, and an AUC of 0.8911. When BERT tokenization was applied, CNN achieved an accuracy of 90.92%, an F1-score of 91.05%, a precision of 90.56%, a recall of 91.55%, and an AUC of 0.9092. LSTM with BERT tokenization obtained an accuracy of 96.84%, an F1-score of 96.79%, a precision of 97.42 a recall of 96.18%, and an AUC of 0.9684. LSTM with the ELECTRA tokenizer achieved an accuracy of 96.92%, an F1-score of 96.82%, a precision of 99.33%, a recall of 94.43%, and an AUC of 0.9692. The combined CNN+LSTM model using the ELECTRA tokenizer demonstrated high performance, reaching an accuracy of 98.11%, an F1-score of 98.07%, a precision of 99.03%, a recall of 97.13%, and an AUC of 0.9811.

3) *Transformer Methods*: Among the transformer models as in Table I, BERT achieved an accuracy of 98.11%, an F1-score of 98.08%, a precision of 98.71%, a recall of 97.45%, and an AUC of 1.0. RoBERTa outperformed all other models, achieving an accuracy of 99.84%, an F1-score of 99.84%, a precision of 100.00%, a recall of 99.68%, and an AUC of 1.0. DistilBERT achieved an accuracy of 96.29%, an F1-score of 96.32%, a precision of 94.76%, a recall of 97.93%, and an AUC of 1.0. ALBERT achieved an accuracy of 97.40%, an F1-score of 97.33%, a precision of 99.01%, a recall of 95.70%, and an AUC of 1.0. ELECTRA achieved an accuracy of 97.55%, an F1-score of 97.50%, a precision of 98.85%, a recall of 96.18%, and an AUC of 1.0. Finally, FinBERT achieved an accuracy of 95.26%, an F1-score of 95.33%, a precision of 93.16%, a recall of 97.61%, and an AUC of 0.99. Overall, deep learning models, particularly transformer-based architectures such as RoBERTa, demonstrated superior performance across all evaluation metrics.

4) *Large Language Model-based Method*: In addition to traditional machine learning and deep learning approaches, LLMs are evaluated for fake news detection through zero-shot prompting techniques, as in figure 6. ChatGPT-5 and ChatGPT-4 were tested by providing news content without prior fine-tuning. Although ChatGPT models demonstrated strong language understanding, their performance was limited when dealing with context-specific and personally sensitive data, resulting in lower consistency in fake news identification.

Fig. 6. Zero-shot-based real/fake detection using LLMs (ChatGPT, Gemini, and DeepSeek).

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE METRICS OF DIFFERENT MODELS AND TOKENIZERS. ROBERTA'S RESULTS ARE HIGHLIGHTED.

Metrics	Random Forest		Gradient Boosting		CNN		LSTM		CNN + LSTM	BERT	Roberta	DistilBERT	ALBERT	ELECTRA	FinBERT
Tokenizer	TfidfVectorizer	BertTokenizer	TfidfVectorizer	BertTokenizer	TfidfVectorizer	BertTokenizer	BertTokenizer	ELECTRA Tokenizer	BertTokenizer	BertTokenizer	RobertaTokenizer	DistilBertTokenizer	AlbertTokenizer	ElectraTokenizer	BertTokenizer
Accuracy	0.9219	0.8958	0.8911	0.9092	0.9140	0.9684	0.9692	0.9811	0.8508	0.9811	0.9984	0.9629	0.9740	0.9755	0.9526
F1 Score	0.9228	0.8946	0.8905	0.9105	0.9138	0.9679	0.9682	0.9807	0.8341	0.9808	0.9984	0.9632	0.9733	0.9750	0.9533
Precision	0.9193	0.9135	0.9034	0.9056	0.9233	0.9742	0.9933	0.9903	0.9295	0.9871	1.0000	0.9476	0.9901	0.9885	0.9316
Recall	0.9264	0.8764	0.8779	0.9155	0.9045	0.9618	0.9443	0.9713	0.7564	0.9745	0.9968	0.9793	0.9570	0.9618	0.9761

Fig. 7. ROC Curve of Transformer Models.

DeepSeek and Gemini, two advanced LLM-based models, exhibited superior performance by accurately classifying real and fake news with higher consistency compared to ChatGPT models. Notably, DeepSeek achieved reliable predictions in cases involving nuanced misinformation, demonstrating its robustness in real-world scenarios. Gemini also showed strong performance, correctly identifying fake and real news articles without the need for additional model tuning. Overall, the results indicated that LLM-based models, particularly

DeepSeek, ChatGPT, and Gemini, are promising tools for fake news detection when designed to handle context-dependent reasoning and domain-specific content.

5) *Summary of Results:* This study evaluates machine learning, deep learning, and LLM-based approaches for fake news detection. Among ensemble models, Random Forest + TF-IDF performs best (92.19% accuracy, 92.28% F1), outperforming Gradient Boosting. Transformer-based deep learning models achieve the strongest results, with **RoBERTa** leading overall (99.84% accuracy/F1, 100.00% precision, 99.68% recall), while DistilBERT, ALBERT, ELECTRA, and FinBERT also exceed 95% accuracy. In addition, zero-shot LLM prompting shows promise, where DeepSeek and Gemini produce more consistent predictions than ChatGPT-3.5/4, particularly for nuanced misinformation. Overall, the results emphasize transformers as the most effective models and highlight LLMs as an emerging option for context-aware classification without extensive fine-tuning.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

In conclusion, our experiments show that fake news detection benefits most from transformer-based models, which consistently deliver the highest accuracy and balanced precision and recall performance. While classical machine learning baselines such as Random Forest with TF-IDF remain strong and computationally efficient, they are clearly surpassed by modern deep learning approaches. In particular, RoBERTa achieves near-perfect results, indicating that contextual language representations are highly effective for capturing subtle misinformation cues. Moreover, the zero-shot LLM setting demonstrates promising potential for flexible, context-

aware classification without task-specific training, although its performance varies across models. Overall, these findings highlight transformers as the most reliable choice for high-performance fake news detection, while LLM-based prompting emerges as a practical complementary direction for adaptable and training-free deployment. For future work, we hope to incorporate a broader range of datasets from diverse domains and sources to enhance model generalization and robustness. While the current experiments are conducted using a single benchmark dataset, the evaluation models were tested across multiple datasets.

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